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Coastal Litter Dynamics in Pangandaran: A DPSIR Framework Investigation of Causes, Consequences, and Solutions

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Abstract

This study employs the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework to explore coastal litter in Pangandaran's coastal areas, analyzing the effects of socio-economic and cultural activities on the environment. Focused on the dynamic coastal ecosystems, it examines how tourism, fishing, and other human activities contribute to environmental degradation through coastal litter, impacting marine life, habitats, and human health, thereby influencing socio-economic outcomes. Pangandaran District serves as a case study to understand the interplay between human activities and environmental pressures, highlighting the challenges of managing coastal litter due to insufficient waste management and low environmental awareness. The research assesses the causality chain within the DPSIR framework, from socio-economic drivers through to the need for strategic responses, including education and sustainable practices aimed at achieving ecological, socio-cultural, and economic sustainability. This concise exploration aims to provide insights into mitigating environmental pressures in coastal areas, advocating for responsible practices and improved waste management to align Pangandaran's development with long-term sustainability objectives, preserving its natural and cultural assets.

Keywords : Coastal litter, DPSIR, Coastal management

Introduction

Coastal regions stand at the intersection of terrestrial and marine ecosystems, significantly influenced by changes originating from both terrestrial and marine sources. These areas are characterized by a dynamic balance between the degradation and formation of terrestrial, marine, and atmospheric elements, making them unique points of convergence. As vital buffer zones, they provide habitat for a diverse array of biological species and are rich in organic matter, contributing to their high fertility levels. This richness endows them with valuable natural resources and development potential, manifested in ecosystems like mangroves, seagrass beds, and coral reefs (Michel, 2010).

Within such contexts, the Pangandaran District in the Pangandaran Regency emerges as a significant case study, renowned for its array of natural, cultural, and man-made tourist attractions, including distinct local culinary experiences. The intense human activity in these coastal regions heightens their susceptibility to pollution, impacting the local economy reliant on fishing and tourism, with a substantial community segment utilizing marine and coastal resources (Rizal et al., 2021).

However, the exploitation of these resources is currently suboptimal and unsustainable. Inadequate management and conservation efforts in coastal areas have led to environmental degradation and pollution. In Indonesia, the damage to coastal and marine ecosystems is predominantly attributed to limited community awareness, with detrimental activities including oil spills, garbage disposal, coastal erosion, mangrove destruction, and tourism impacts, all resulting from human interventions (Vatria, 2010). This backdrop necessitates a focused research approach utilizing the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework to meticulously analyze marine litter challenges in the Pangandaran sub-district, especially around Pangandaran Beach. The DPSIR framework offers a systematic methodology to assess and manage environmental risks through a cause-and-effect relationship, highlighting its effectiveness in identifying socio-economic and socio-cultural drivers of human actions that exacerbate or alleviate environmental pressures. These actions significantly influence the environmental state, affecting the ecosystem and culminating in impacts that require strategic management and action evaluations (Troian et al., 2021; GRID Arendal, 2005; Pirrone et al., 2005).

Therefore, the objective of this study is to scrutinize the environmental pressures and impacts exerted by tourism, fishing, maritime transport, and land runoff on Pangandaran's coastal areas. It aims to pinpoint the primary sources of coastal litter and assess how socio-economic and cultural advancements, notably in the tourism and fishing sectors, impose pressures on the coastal environment. This analysis will extend to evaluating the current state of waste management and environmental consciousness in Pangandaran, its implications on marine life, habitats, coastal aesthetics, and human health, ultimately leading to socio-economic setbacks. The study's core ambition is to devise and appraise local government initiatives in education, waste management training, and sustainable practices, focusing on achieving ecological, socio-cultural, and economic sustainability. By promoting responsible tourism and fishing practices that bolster the local economy and ecosystem health, this research endeavors to ensure Pangandaran's developmental trajectory aligns with comprehensive sustainability objectives, without omitting the scholarly sources that underpin these insights.

Methodology

The DPSIR (Driving Forces-Pressures-State-Impact-Responses) framework is elucidated with reference to scholarly sources as follows.

Driving Forces:

This involves the identification of key environmental change drivers such as economic growth, demographic shifts, and technological advancements. These elements exert environmental pressures (Tscherning et al., 2012).

Pressures:

This step entails identifying pressures generated by driving forces like pollutant emissions and natural resource exploitation. Efforts should be made to quantify these pressures where feasible (Gupta et al., 2019).

State:

This involves assessing the current environmental or system condition, covering aspects like water, air, soil quality, and biodiversity (Patrício et al., 2016).

Impact:

This analysis focuses on the environmental condition impacts on human health, ecosystems, and economic sustainability. It aims to identify both negative and positive consequences of environmental changes (Gari et al., 2015).

Responses:

This entails the design and evaluation of policy, technological, or practice responses that can lessen pressures, improve environmental conditions, or mitigate negative impacts. Such responses may include regulatory policies, economic incentives, or technological innovations (Lewison et al., 2016).

Existing research indicates that the DPSIR framework serves as an effective tool for decision-making support by presenting concrete evidence alongside decision alternatives and options (Tscherning et al., 2012). It underscores the importance of developing conceptual models that integrate knowledge from various scientific disciplines, stakeholder engagement, and the provision of alternatives to enhance evidence-based decision-making processes.

Results and Discussion

The research findings indicate that the lowest Impact Ratio (IR) potentially causing the highest impact and pressure on the environment is coastal litter. This debris, resulting from tourism activities, fishing operations, sea transportation, and land runoff discarded by humans in coastal or marine environments, either intentionally or unintentionally, is a significant environmental concern (Tuahatu & Tuhumury, 2022). Field observations and interviews with local communities around Pangandaran Beach reveal that the majority of coastal waste originates from market waste, leftover food, plastic, and fishing gear, whereas coastal litter primarily consists of plastic waste of various sizes (megadebris and microdebris). The presence of coastal waste is attributed to human activities or is brought from other places by currents, with unknown quantities and routes. Coastal litter directly affects marine biota, habitats, aesthetic impacts on coastal environments, and human health, leading to losses in various socio-economic aspects dependent on coastal and marine environments (Johan et al., 2020).

This study employs the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR) framework to organize insights from literature on the pressing issue of coastal litter in the Pangandaran sub-district, particularly along Pangandaran Beach. The DPSIR framework is utilized to assess and manage environmental risks by considering a linear cause-effect relationship chain, widely adopted in environmental studies (Troian et al., 2021; GRID Arendal, 2005). In this framework, socio-economic and socio-cultural drivers motivate human activities that can either increase or decrease environmental pressures. These activities affect the environment, reflected in the state, which can cause impacts on ecosystems, eventually leading to responses as evaluations of actions in terms of management strategies (Pirrone et al., 2005).

- **Drivers**

The waste and pollution issues in this area are influenced by economic sector growth, namely tourism and fishing activities, which increase the number of tourists and residents at certain times. Data shows fluctuations in tourist numbers over the past five years, indicating ongoing development in the tourism sector. Without

proper management, this can escalate environmental pressures. Additionally, the high activity levels of fishermen and the traffic of motorized wooden boats have been identified as significant sources of pressure. The area's potential in tourism and fishing sectors plays a crucial role in economic enhancement and pressure levels.

- **Pressure**

The pressures from these drivers significantly affect the coastal environment. The research highlights that the greatest pressure comes from coastal litter found in coastal and marine environments. Sources of this waste include debris from tourist spots, fishing gear, household or homestay waste, and marine-derived debris. The accumulation of coastal litter and waste increases during the holiday season. Tourists' and locals' behavior, characterized by a lack of environmental awareness, drives the increase in improper waste disposal. This aligns with Boelee et al. (2019), who noted the influence of socio-economic conditions on human behavior and environmental pressure.
- **State**

Pangandaran sub-district has 9 Waste Collection Points (WCPs) with a capacity of 48 m³. Daily waste collection by sanitation workers does not guarantee uniform cleanliness. The lack of environmental care among residents and tourists results in litter scattered along main access roads, especially near shopping centers. Fishermen's disregard for the environment leads to the disposal of fishing gear waste along the coast. The appearance of waste and water spillage around fish sales areas contributes to a dirty and unsightly environment, posing health risks, reducing aesthetic value, causing economic losses, and disrupting natural systems.
- **Impact**

Deteriorating environmental conditions have adverse effects on surrounding ecosystems and human well-being. The accumulation of waste and suboptimal management in coastal areas can lead to diseases. Waste and unkempt environments become breeding grounds for harmful bacteria, damaging environmental components through contamination (Permadi & Murni, 2013).
- **Response**

Ultimately, responses address the overall drivers, pressures, states, and impacts. Local government efforts include education and waste management training. However, these measures are ineffective without support from district services and increased human awareness. Government actions align with each DPSIR framework component, such as:

 1. **Drivers:** Environmental and cleanliness department initiatives on waste management through 3R (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) principles and community, fishermen, and tourist education on proper waste disposal. Awareness campaigns for beach visitors have been conducted (Apriliani et al., 2021), showing that lectures/discussions and beach cleanup activities improve environmental awareness among target audiences. Rizal et al. (2021) also reported increased community awareness towards coastal environment preservation through their outreach.
 2. **States:** Provision of waste sorting facilities every 500 m along main access roads and frequent trash collection points.

- Impact

While the community recognizes the importance of environmental preservation, visitor behavior changes and occasional neglect lead to pollution. 4.6 Management Goals The responses within the DPSIR framework aim to adhere to ecological physical principles and expand to accommodate various government

Conclusion

This study identifies coastal litter, originating from tourism, fishing, sea transport, and land runoff, as the most significant environmental pressure and impact in coastal areas, particularly affecting Pangandaran. This debris harms marine life, habitats, coastal aesthetics, and human health, leading to socio-economic losses. Using the DPSIR (Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response) framework, the research evaluates how socio-economic and cultural drivers, such as tourism and fishing industry growth, create pressures on the coastal environment. Increased waste, especially during tourist seasons, and a general lack of environmental awareness exacerbate these pressures. Pangandaran's current state reflects inadequate waste management and a lack of environmental consciousness among residents and tourists, leading to pollution and health hazards. The impact of this situation extends to ecosystem degradation and potential disease outbreaks due to unmanaged waste and pollution. The response to these challenges involves local government initiatives in education, waste management training, and sustainable practices across the DPSIR framework. Management goals focus on achieving ecological, social-cultural, and economic sustainability, promoting responsible tourism and fishing practices that support the local economy and ecosystem health. Efforts include enhancing environmental awareness, supporting sustainable waste management, and encouraging eco-friendly tourism and fishing practices to ensure Pangandaran's future development aligns with ecological, cultural, and economic sustainability goals.

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